

Although no one can yet forecast if or when it will become an operational technology, quantum computing R&D efforts will nevertheless have a profound impact on the future of computing as it is boosting research in important topics such as hybrid architectures, and algorithmic and computational complexity. It also forces us to re-think the very nature of information processing.

Towards operational quantum computing? Or: thinking beyond qubits

By Christian Gamrat

The paper published in Nature by the Google team in late 2019 took the computing community by storm. However, if quantum supremacy - or more realistically, operational quantum computing - ever becomes a reality, it will probably not be the result of a milestone event. It could materialize in very specific fields, mostly unnoticed, and will be very progressive. The fact is that quantum computing must first address huge engineering challenges, in both hardware systems and software. At the same time, classical and algorithmic computing are progressing, as is our understanding of application needs and computational complexity.

Quantum supremacy is a moving target. It moves according to progress in non-quantum information processing and our better understanding of when and how to tackle hard problems. Quantum computing is and will remain a hybrid computing approach in which advances in the fields of quantum, classical and artificial intelligence (AI) computing will enrich each other. This is why the system and software stacks making up the future quantum computer will be an important area for future developments. It is probably the right time to think beyond the qubit.

Key insights

- No matter what, a quantum computer will be a cloud-based hybrid classical/quantum computer. HPC infrastructures will be the ideal playground for developing such a hybrid system stack.
- A consequence of the "cloudification" of quantum computing could trigger a move towards a European quantum cloud, similar to EBRAINS [21], as seen in the Human Brain project.
- R&D in system architecture and software stack for quantum computing (QC) needs to be pushed. With European assets in the system, software and HPC technologies this could be a good opportunity for Europe.
- The fields of quantum computing and AI are becoming closer. This might appear to be the result of a buzzword strategy but there are real scientific and technological reasons behind the scenes.
- Quantum computing sheds new light on computational complexity theory. It appears to be the ideal tool to rejuvenate basic research in the field of information theory.
- Fears emerged that the longer-term research needed to tackle QC might be negatively impacted by new funding strategies in the aftermath of COVID-19, but the potential impact of QC will probably prevail.
- Startups in quantum computing are emerging. Europe is on the right path.

Key recommendations

- Support R&D in the field of architecture and software stacks for quantum computing.
- Develop the integration of quantum accelerators into future exascale infrastructure.
- Promote the development of a European quantum cloud.

Quantum computing is a rapidly developing field. It is currently raising a lot of hopes and creating a lot of noise both in the world of research and in the world of industry. In principle, the realization of machines applying quantum principles could make it possible to deal with problems that are difficult or impossible to tackle with conventional computers. The applications fields that would benefit the most from quantum computing are those with problems incurring an exponentially large number of variables with respect to the size of the problem. Such problems are often found in chemistry, pharmacology, physics, cryptography, optimization and machine learning.

However, the design of a quantum computer capable of operating efficiently on these problems remains a long-term prospect. At the hardware level, the realization of the indispensable qubits with potential for sufficient fidelity and scalability is a major research field with several technologies being actively investigated. Superconducting qubits have pioneered the development of quantum computing and have been demonstrated [1]. They are now playing a role in the development of a spin qubit technology based on silicon semiconductors [2]. At the application and algorithmic level, there is a broad range of work on various platforms. There is clearly a gap between experimental efforts at the hardware level and more theoretical research at the algorithmic level.

In a paper published in Nature, a Google/NASA team claimed to have reached quantum supremacy [3]. Quantum supremacy is defined as “the potential ability of quantum devices to solve problems that classical computers practically cannot” and was initially introduced by John Preskill [4]. The Google/NASA team actually achieved this but on a rather limited problem. In fact, they used a 54 superconducting qubits chip (the “Sycamore chip”) with nearest neighbours’ interactions to run a circuit that generated near perfect random

sequences of bits. It’s just like rolling a dice with several millions of faces instead of just six. Indeed, to simulate a near perfect distribution over rolling such a dice with a powerful classical computer it could take a fair amount of time. In the paper they estimate that it would take 10,000 years if run on the best Google servers and require a few PW (10^{15} Watts) of electrical power. They claimed the Sycamore chip can do the same computation (generate a sequence of several million random numbers) in 600 seconds using as little as 10 kW of power. That’s a really impressive result! Does this mean that quantum computing is ready, that the race is over, and we shall all start ditching our good old classical computers? Not so fast.

The fact is, if some sort of quantum advantage was demonstrated, it was on a rather useless application. Nevertheless, the scientific achievements were important as the paper demonstrated that errors do not depend on entanglement and computational complexity, that no new decoherence physics was detected (an indication that error correction algorithms should be working) and that quantum computing works on a rather large system. If this paper did not show that quantum computing is ready for real applications, it showed that its basic principles seem to be valid.

Qubit technologies update

Besides progress in qubit technologies, one of the main questions that need to be tackled on the road to operational QC is that of scalability. Depending on the qubit implementation technology, the challenges may vary but one that sticks is the problem of noise. The term noise refers to the impact of various factors leading to a loss of precision of the qubits states (Figure 1). Those factors can result from fabrication imperfections, sensitivity to parasitic signals, crosstalk, material degradation, etc. Digital computing technologies such as CMOS are facing many of the same problems; after all, a CMOS transistor also suffers from noise, parasitic interferences and crosstalk but the difference is that the classical binary coding scheme provides an efficient shield against those underlying sources of noise.

Hybrid HPC quantum and the quantum cloud

A quantum computer cannot work without a classical Von-Neumann type computer! Indeed, if quantum information processing can bring benefits in terms of parallelization of massive calculations (superposition of states), it will not bring anything significant in logic and control operations. Moreover, the problems we are interested in solving along with their potential solutions exist in our very classical world. Therefore, a quantum computer is and will remain a hybrid-computing

Figure 1: Evolution of lifetime and coherence time of superconducting qubits. From Kjaergaard et al.

machine with a “boring” classical computer doing the input/output interface and probably a big bulk of the data-processing logic. We have then the concept of a quantum accelerator core that, just like a GPU core, can speed up graphical computations or, like an FPGA, can speed up specific tasks hand-in-hand with their host processor (Figure 2).

Most of the application domains that would benefit from quantum computing involve extremely large sets of variables. These domains include chemistry, physics, cryptography and machine learning. Such applications can only be processed using large computing infrastructures. A typical example being artificial intelligence in which it is common to have embedded processors (in a portable device, in a car) running the inference phase (e.g. pattern recognition/classification) while the computationally heavy machine learning phase is offloaded onto a HPC server. Large computing platforms are therefore the primary target for the integration of quantum accelerators and the development of hybrid quantum-classical programming methodologies. This is for example what the Jülich UNified Infrastructure for Quantum computing (JUNIQ) is currently introducing [22] (Figure 3). JUNIQ will integrate quantum computers (e.g. ATOS QLM) and quantum annealers (e.g. D-Wave) in the form of quantum-classical hybrid computing systems into the modular HPC environment of the Jülich Supercomputing Centre.

On another level, QuTech in the Netherlands (TNO and TU-Delft) has introduced a quantum computing platform to help run and evaluate quantum algorithms on a variety of simulators or hardware [5, 23] (Figure 4). With this platform the focus is put on the ease of access to a quantum simulation environment for experimenting with quantum processing on both simulated and real hardware platforms.

Those European based QC platforms represent a bold move towards offering state of the art quantum hardware and quantum programming tools to both industry and academic users in addition to the online platforms already proposed by the likes of Google (Cirq) [6], IBM (QisKit), DWave,

Figure 2: Perspective of a Hybrid Classical-Quantum computing architecture based on single photon source qubits as proposed by the Quandela startup company (<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-19341-4>)

Figure 3: JUNIQ is a uniform quantum computing Platform as a Service (QC-PaaS) proposed by the Jülich Supercomputer center.

Figure 4: The QI Editor from Quantum Inspire allows users to write, run and test quantum algorithms online.

IONQ or Microsoft (QDK). The advent of European cloud-based quantum computing platforms might also mitigate some confidentiality and sovereignty concerns. The recent announcement by ATOS of the quantum metrics reference “Q-Score” [24], which aims to benchmark and measure the capacity of quantum processors to solve real problems will also help experimentation with the effectiveness of quantum computing.

Toward a system and software stack for quantum computing

As the trend towards integrating quantum accelerated processors with classical (probably CMOS based) computers accelerates, the need arises to develop specific system architectures and software layers that will orchestrate the execution of both classical and quantum circuits required to run real applications.

However, to achieve this goal, it is necessary to address the huge gap between the current experimental efforts at the qubits level and the more theoretical research at the quantum algorithmic level. In order to bridge the gap, we need to design an architecture (hardware, software and system) that will allow the programming and the execution of applications on the available quantum technology.

This architecture will make it possible to link a “software stack” made up of languages, compilers and other tools for the description of applications and their algorithms with an “execution stack” responsible for the orchestration of the physical circuits. If the software/hardware duality is at the heart of modern digital computing systems, it will also be the case for quantum computers in addition to the classical/quantum duality. Therefore, as said earlier, a quantum computer will be composed of a set of quantum operators acting on qubits tightly coupled with a set of classical processors realizing a hybrid computing architecture. Just like in modern microprocessors, the efficiency of a future quantum computer will depend, for a large part, on the design of the hybrid interfaces: software/hardware, classical/quantum. The key role of the software and architecture stack for quantum computing has been highlighted in pioneering work by the University of Delft [7] (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Bridging the gap between physical qubit technologies and applications and experiments on operational quantum computers, through the development of the system and software stack (part from @fu2016).

Although software platforms for hybrid programming have recently been proposed [6] (in particular in the field of machine learning), they are still either too abstract or too proprietary to allow for a simple interface with the physical qubits currently under development. However, they represent a starting point that would be useful as a basis for a coordinated R&D effort and help bridge the gap between physical qubits and high-level quantum algorithms. Software and system research is often overlooked and considered as a “simple” engineering endeavour. It is however the quality of the system stack that will make the difference between an experiment with qubits and an operational quantum computer. We believe that, together with a strong position in cloud-based quantum infrastructure, a healthy and well-supported research base in the field of system architecture and software stack has the potential to put Europe at the forefront of quantum computing.

Quantum computing boosts research in computational complexity

A recent work [8] shed further light on quantum supremacy by introducing theoretical elements showing that such a supremacy could be challenged on a classical laptop computer if limitations of real quantum computers are taken into

account. The paper acknowledges the fact that perfect quantum computers are exponentially difficult to simulate on a classical computer. However real quantum computers are not and will likely never be perfect and will suffer from various sources of decoherence and imprecision. If those limiting factors are considered when designing an algorithm for a classical computer, then the authors [8] shows that the simulation time can be drastically reduced. This remark on simulation time of a real quantum computer stresses the importance of computational complexity (Figure 6).

Paradoxically we might face a situation in which we solve most QC challenges, build the QC, program the QC and finally end up in a situation where the horizon of “quantum supremacy” has been pushed away by better knowledge of and progress made in problem solving.

Research in quantum can also have good side effects: low temperature electronics for controlling and interfacing qubits can lead to cryogenic computing, and research in quantum algorithms can also improve classical algorithms: as an example, the young Ewin Tang has proven that classical computers can solve the “recommendation problem” nearly as fast as quantum comput-

Figure 6: Overview of complexity classes, including Bounded-error Quantum Polynomial time (BQP)

ers. The recommendation problem relates to how services like Amazon and Netflix determine which products you might like to try. Computer scientists had considered it to be one of the best examples of a problem that's exponentially faster to solve on quantum computers — like Kerenidis and Prakash's algorithm [9], Tang's algorithm ran in polylogarithmic time (meaning the computational time scaled with the logarithm of characteristics like the number of users and products in the data set) and was exponentially faster than any previously known classical algorithm [10].

This example shows that regardless of the actual availability of QC hardware, rethinking algorithms and programming in the light of quantum information brings a new vision on the actual limits of computer problem solving. Quantum supremacy is a moving target.

The QC and AI entanglement

Quantum computing and artificial intelligence are often cited like a winning combination. A number of recent scientific works emphasized the interactions between these two technologies [11]. It is hard to tell if this will become a reality or if this is just the result of a buzzwords strategy.

Machine learning (ML), which is at the heart of the current incarnation of AI, is a multi-parametric optimization prob-

lem and it can in principle benefit from advances in QC or quantum annealing. At the same time, progress in ML and AI can also offer benefits to QC. It is particularly true in the field of quantum state measurements. Machine learning-based measurement protocols have shown interesting results with both supervised [12] and unsupervised [13] learning methods.

Google has released an open source library aimed at bridging the gap between AI and quantum computing: "TensorFlow Quantum" [25]. In fact TensorFlow Quantum (TFQ) is the result of a merging of the TensorFlow library (TF) and the Google Quantum circuit simulator CIRQ [6].

Will quantum computing boosted by AI be able to actually help solve real problems in a foreseeable future? In some ways, AI techniques with their abilities to capture hidden mechanisms might be part of the path to a solution. However, even AI is not magic, and it has been shown many times that in order to be efficient, AI methods need a little help from experts. That is to say: some physical knowledge (in our case quantum mechanics) has to be added into the overall equation.

Like we said earlier, it was an obvious observation that a quantum computer will be a hybrid classical-quantum machine, but we also come to realize that QC might even

be more of a hybrid than that! It is quite possible that quantum computing could only be achieved as the result of a close coupling between quantum and machine learning techniques and algorithms: the quantum-AI hybridization.

Are we heading towards a QC winter ?

Recently, several news items have highlighted the idea that investments in QC could be significantly affected in comparison to recent times [14-17] (Figure 7). Another indicator is the fact that most of the over-hyped announcements by IBM, Google, Intel and others are still very far from being ready for real applications. Finally, the announcement of John Martinis' resignation from Google [18] might have raised suspicion about the confidence that the company behind the 2019 Quantum Supremacy announcement has in the rapid development of QC. Officially, Martinis said he had resigned because Google was putting him off the executive role in its Quantum research unit [19]. However, it is not difficult to understand that, as a respected scientist, Martinis' agenda for QC is probably different from Google's corporate agenda. Indeed, claiming "quantum supremacy" in Nature does not mean that an operational quantum computer will soon be ready for real applications. There were actually two possible readings in Google's paper: on one side the corporate reading for the investors, mainly the title and abstract, expecting rapid return on investments. On the other side was the scientific reading for the academics, who saw a very nice experiment on fundamental (albeit not directly applicable) aspects of quantum computing. Obviously, the time frame of both readings does not stick to the same roadmap.

QC startups in Europe

A number of startup companies in the field of quantum computing have emerged over the last few years [20] (Table 1). Even if a few are just consultancy companies, a number of them are developing and marketing hardware, software or communication products. Their activities range from development of single photon sources that could fuel quantum networks or photonic based quantum computing (Qandela) to designing complete quantum

Figure 7: Quantum computing hype cycle https://extremecomputingtraining.anl.gov/files/2019/08/ATPESC_2019_Dinner_Talk_9_8-8_Alexeev-QC_Trends.pdf

processors with atomic arrays (PasQal). Some are working on developing software IPs for enterprise and industrial customers (AppliedQubit), while others are developing quantum software platforms for drug discovery (ApexQubit), or working in the field of quantum-secured communications (ID Quantique) and quantum network technologies and distributed quantum computing (VeriQloud).

	Hardware	Software	Communication
France	5	2	2
Germany	2	3	3
Greece		1	
Italy		1	
Norway		1	
Poland		2	
Spain	2	4	
Sweden	1		
Switzerland	2		1
The Netherlands	4	2	
UK	7	6	11
Other	3	5	1
Total	26	27	18

Table 1: The QC startup landscape Europe (from <https://quantumcomputingreport.com/privatestartup/>)

References

[1] D. Vion et al., "Manipulating the Quantum State of an Electrical Circuit," *Science*, vol. 296, no. 5569, pp. 886–889, May 2002, doi: 10.1126/science.1069372.

[2] R. Maurand et al., "A CMOS silicon spin qubit," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 7, p. 13575, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1038/ncomms13575.

[3] F. Arute et al., "Quantum supremacy using a programmable superconducting processor," *Nature*, vol. 574, no. 7779, pp. 505–510, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-1666-5.

[4] J. Preskill, "Quantum computing and the entanglement frontier," *ArXiv12035813 Cond-Mat Physicsquant-Ph*, Mar. 2012, Accessed: Nov. 11, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1203.5813>.

[5] TNO, "Minister Ingrid van Engelshoven and European Commissioner Mariya Gabriel launch Europe's first quantum computer in the cloud: Quantum Inspire," TNO, Apr. 2020. [en/about-tno/news/2020/4/europe-s-first-quantum-computer-in-the-cloud-quantum-inspire/](https://www.tno.nl/en/about-tno/news/2020/4/europe-s-first-quantum-computer-in-the-cloud-quantum-inspire/) (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[6] M. Broughton et al., "TensorFlow Quantum: A Software Framework for Quantum Machine Learning," *ArXiv200302989 Cond-Mat Physicsquant-Ph*, Mar. 2020, Accessed: Mar. 10, 2020. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2003.02989>.

[7] X. Fu et al., "A Heterogeneous Quantum Computer Architecture," in *Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers*, New York, NY, USA, 2016, pp. 323–330, doi: 10.1145/2903150.2906827.

[8] Y. Zhou, E. M. Stoudenmire, and X. Waintal, "What Limits the Simulation of Quantum Computers?," *Phys. Rev. X*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 041038, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevX.10.041038.

[9] I. Kerenidis and A. Prakash, "Quantum gradient descent for linear systems and least squares," *ArXiv170404992 Quant-Ph*, Apr. 2017, Accessed: Aug. 02, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1704.04992>.

[10] E. Tang, "A quantum-inspired classical algorithm for recommendation systems," *ArXiv180704271 Quant-Ph*, Jul. 2018, Accessed: Aug. 02, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1807.04271>.

[11] R. G. Melko, G. Carleo, J. Carrasquilla, and J. I. Cirac, "Restricted Boltzmann machines in quantum physics," *Nat. Phys.*, vol. 15, no. 9, pp. 887–892, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41567-019-0545-1.

[12] V. Havlicek et al., "Supervised learning with quantum-enhanced feature spaces," *Nature*, vol. 567, no. 7747, pp. 209–212, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41586-019-0980-2.

[13] K. A. McKiernan, E. Davis, M. S. Alam, and C. Rigetti, "Automated quantum programming via reinforcement learning for combinatorial optimization," *ArXiv190808054 Quant-Ph*, Aug. 2019, Accessed: Nov. 30, 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1908.08054>.

[14] E. Gent, "Investment in Quantum Computing Is Booming—But Will a Quantum Winter Follow?," *Singularity Hub*, Oct. 14, 2019. <https://singularityhub.com/2019/10/14/investment-in-quantum-computing-is-booming-but-will-a-quantum-winter-follow/> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[15] M. Swayne, "Quantum Winter? Is the Red Hot Quantum Startup Space About to Turn Ice Cold?," *The Quantum Daily*, Mar. 09, 2020. <https://thequantumdaily.com/2020/03/09/quantum-winter-is-the-red-hot-quantum-startup-space-about-to-turn-ice-cold/> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[16] InsideQuantumTechnology, "Quantum Winter' a Concern," *Inside Quantum Technology*, 2020. <https://www.insidequantumtechnology.com/news/quantum-winter-concern/> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[17] "Quantum Computing in 2021," *Strategic Finance*. <https://sfmagazine.com/technotes/december-2020-quantum-computing-in-2021/> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[18] Wired, "Google's Head of Quantum Computing Hardware Resigns," *Wired*, Apr. 2020.

[19] M. I. and Strategy, "Google's Top Quantum Scientist Explains In Detail Why He Resigned," *Forbes*, Apr. 2020. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/moorinsights/2020/04/30/googles-top-quantum-scientist-explains-in-detail-why-he-resigned/> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[20] "Quantum gold rush: the private funding pouring into quantum start-ups," <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-019-02935-4> (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[21] "EBRAINS is powering a new era in Brain Research," <https://ebrains.eu>, (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[22] "JUNIQ - Jülich UNified Infrastructure for Quantum computing," https://www.fz-juelich.de/ias/jsc/EN/Expertise/JUNIQ_node.html, (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[23] "The multi hardware Quantum Technology platform," <https://www.quantum-inspire.com>, (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[24] "Q-score: Measure what truly matters," <https://atos.net/en/solutions/q-score>, (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

[25] "TensorFlow Quantum is a library for hybrid quantum-classical machine learning" <https://www.tensorflow.org/quantum>, (accessed Jan. 12, 2021).

Christian Gamrat is a researcher at the Research and Technology Department of CEA (Alternative energies and Atomic Energy Commission), France.

This document is part of the HiPEAC Vision available at hipeac.net/vision.

This is release v.1, January 2021.

Cite as: C. Gamrat. Towards operational quantum computing? Or: thinking beyond qubits. In M. Duranton et al., editors, *HiPEAC Vision 2021*, pages 116-121, Jan 2021.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4719630

The HiPEAC project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 871174.

© HiPEAC 2021